

Additional file 5. qRT-PCR validation of RNA-Seq experiments. Correlation of RNA-Seq and qRT-PCR expression ratios for the seven genes with various expression levels and genomic locations. The gene expression ratios obtained from both qRT-PCR and RNA-Seq were normalized by a housekeeping control gene Efm745_00056 (*tufA*). The experiments was performed with three biological replicates.